

TASK-ORIENTED LEADERSHIP STYLE AND PERFORMANCE OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The paper discussed the application of the task-oriented leadership style in addressing specific educational problems in Nigerian public educational institutions. The paper adopted secondary data for the collection of data. The secondary data were obtained from print and online publications. The paper concluded that a task-oriented leadership style can be used for specific school problems. The paper also discovered that a task-oriented leadership style can be used to improve teachers' job performance and students' academic performance in educational institutions in Nigeria. Based on this, the paper recommended that school administrators in Nigeria should learn more about task-oriented leadership styles for application in providing quality leadership in their respective schools and the government should expose school administrators to constant capacity-building programmes that are leadership style inclined.*

Keywords: *School administrator, Teachers' job performance, Students' academic performance.*

Introduction

The school is an educational institution where teaching and learning take place. School is a social environment designed for teaching and learning. The school has an objective to achieve. Adeyemo (2001) noted that the major goal of the school is to work towards the attainment of academic excellence of the students by the teachers.

School is designed to operate with the students, teachers and school administrators. The students are regarded as the king in educational institutions. The students are learners. The students depend on the teachers for instruction. The students are a critical component of the school system. The student's academic performance matter to every stakeholder in the educational institutions.

In the roles of the teachers in the schools, the teachers are regarded as the implementer of the school curriculum. The job of the teachers includes; implementation of curriculum, planning of lesson notes, lesson plan, organization of instructional resources, assessment of students via continuous assessment and examination, marking of students' scripts and provision of feedback to parents on students' academic performance. Ogunode (2021a); Ogunode (2021b) and Olowonefa & Ogunode (2021) observed that teachers are fundamental to the effective delivery of the teaching programme in educational institutions. The teachers' place in educational institutions cannot be replaced. The teacher plans the lesson, organizes the instructional

resources and delivers the lesson. The teachers ensure the students learn the right knowledge and skills through the process of teaching and learning. Teachers are found in all educational institutions.

Muhammed & Ogunode (2021) opined that one of the basic functions of school administrators is to ensure that teaching and learning take place and to ensure this, the school administrator needs adequate and quality teachers. School administrators need teachers to implement the curriculum. School administrators are powerless without teachers. The teachers determine the success of the school administrators.

In respect of the roles of school administrators, the school administrator according to Muhammed et al (2021) also known as principal appointed by the ministries of education to head public secondary schools across the country. Appointment of principals or school administrators is based on seniority in service. In Nigeria, the position of the principalship is based on experience and promotion. This is because the Nigerian civil service relies mostly on years of experience and promotion to elevate people from one cadre to the other, especially from the classroom to the management levels (Dubi, 2014).

School administrators are appointed to help in the realization of the objectives of the schools. The function of the school Principals/School administrators includes administration of teachers, coordination of student programmes, resources allocation and physical resources application, and school community relationship management (Muhammed et al, 2021). Ornstein (2008) viewed the functions of the principal as setting instructional directions, result-oriented, team management, organizational coordination ability, effective communication, development of others and developing self. Dubi (2014) submitted that all the functions the principal discharges daily are geared towards the fulfilment of the objectives of the school

Muhammed et al (2021) submitted that school leadership is very vital to the actualization of the school objectives. Leadership has been identified as a crucial factor in instructional effectiveness. It is a major factor in determining the success and progress of an institution. It is the key to success in every organization because it can either influence the climate of the school positively or negatively. Without effective leadership, even an institution full of talented teachers will surely drift without purpose. It is therefore key to achieving collective excellence. It is the leader who most greatly affects the organisational climate and provides direction, motivation and inspiration for the school (Dubi 2014). In other words, the success of any institution depends largely on the ability of the leader to maintain a conducive environment for the development of its members. Wanyoko, & Muchanje, (2021) stated that school leadership is important as it provides direction for the institution. It is the dream of every leader to achieve the set goals and attain success. Achieving the set objectives requires a school leader to offer directions to the teachers, students and other members of staff in the school working for the benefit of the students. For school leaders to achieve the set goals, great cooperation is required between teachers and the administrator. Principals steer the schools in the direction they want them to go because they are the major decision-makers in the school.

School administrators have opportunities to adopt different leadership styles that best suit the situation of their schools. Leadership styles are very important in school management and administration. It provides opportunities for school leaders to solve pressing school challenges. According to Yusuf (2012), no school can be greater than its leader. School administrators must be able to incorporate and balance all tasks entrusted to their responsibility.

Educational institutions in Nigeria are plagued with different challenges that require the adoption of different leadership styles to solve them. Poor students' academic performance has been

identified as a major problem facing majorities of schools in Nigeria (Ogunode, 2021; Ogunode & Ajape 2021; Ogunode & Abara 2021; Ogunode & Ugboime 2021; Edeh, 2021; Abah, Edeh & Nwakamma, 2016). Another major challenge is the low job performance of teachers in most public educational institutions across the country. School administrators in Nigeria are faced with the challenges of adopting the right and most effective leadership style to address these problems in the educational system. This paper is aimed to discuss the importance of the task-oriented leadership style as the style that can be used to address the problems of poor students' academic performance and low teachers' job performances in public secondary schools across the country.

Concept of Task-Oriented Leadership Style

Task-oriented leadership style has different definitions given by different scholars. Online.stu.edu (2014) viewed a task-oriented leader as one that emphasizes the tasks needed to achieve goals. Task-oriented leadership is “doing whatever it takes to get the job done. Task-oriented leadership often is contrasted against relations-oriented leadership. The approach tends to be autocratic and emphasizes completing tasks required to meet organizational goals. Jenn, (2019) observed that task-oriented leadership focuses on achieving goals. Task-oriented leaders delegate assignments, set clear processes and issue deadlines to ensure all team members remain focused and deliver their part of the project within the designated time. Managers of the school who use this style develop a structured workplace with clearly defined priorities and schedules for administrative staffs and teachers.

Carter (undated) viewed task-oriented leadership as a directive style of leadership specifying tasks and goals. Task-oriented leaders provide steps and a plan to meet the goals of an organization. In task-oriented leadership, the leader can achieve a specific standard of performance in their direction. Okumbe (2001) described task-oriented personnel as those with no concern for the welfare of the workers. He or she is a workaholic and has no confidence in his or her subordinates.

For Forsyth & Donelson (2010), task-oriented leadership is a behavioural approach, in which the leader focuses on the tasks that need to be performed to meet certain goals or to achieve a certain performance standard. The task-oriented leadership style covers some features of task management. Task management, requires coordination of job-related activities, giving importance to administrative activities, supervising teaching-learning delivery quality and preparing financial reports. Thus, it can be concluded that leaders who adopt a task-oriented leadership style, focus on completing necessary tasks to reach organizational targets. One of the distinctive characteristics of these leaders is that they are less concerned with the employees, who are the critical agents to achieve the desired goals. On the contrary, they are more concerned with following a planned path to achieve specific organizational targets. Goddey (2017) saw task-oriented leaders as leaders that focus only on getting the job done, and could be quite autocratic. They actively define the work and roles required, put structures in place, plan, organize, coordinate, direct and monitor. However, since task-oriented leaders do not tend to think much about the well-being of their employees, this approach could suffer many of the flaws of autocratic leadership with difficulties in motivating and retaining employees.

From the above definitions, task-oriented leadership can be defined as goal-inclined and focused leaders in the school that ensure the completion of school objectives within a timeframe. Task-oriented leaders in the school setting define the roles of the whole teachers specifically in the schools and provide teaching resources for the teachers to carry out their teaching assignments. The task-oriented leaders provide instructional materials for the teachers, and other educational

resources to get the job done. In this kind of leadership in school, everything is focused on achieving the school tasks and goals. Task-oriented school leadership is a school leadership model in that the school leaders' priority is getting tasks done through the use of the teachers' goal setting and definition. Task-oriented school leaders tend to be more focused on creating step-by-step plans to achieve the school's objectives. Tasks-oriented leaders in school are very organized, creating structures and systems for their teachers to excel in the school tasks.

Tasks-oriented leaders in school create clearly defined roles for each teacher and administrative staffs. Tasks-oriented leaders in schools make sure teachers are on track with their school work. A task-focused school leader employs performance review methods to assess the teachers' productivity and care less about their emotional feeling at work. Task-oriented leaders in the school know how to appoint teachers to various offices according to the teacher's strengths, competencies, and roles within the time limit required in the school calendar. Task-oriented leaders in the schools understand that the school has limited resources and so they make defined plans to assign the work to highly effective and efficient teachers to meet the closing date. In doing this in the school, the school leader can achieve results more successfully than any other kind of leadership style.

The advantages of task-oriented school leaders include the following;

1. **Achieve School Goals:** Task-inclined leaders are always goal attainment inclined and because of this they deploy SMART strategies (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Time-bound) which help them create more realistic goals for the school and teachers. This help to realize the school's objectives.
2. **Meet School Deadlines:** When school leaders focused on getting school work done, this helps them to meet all of the school deadlines. Setting a clear school deadline gives teachers a chance to work ahead on school-specific projects and tasks.
3. **Straightforward Leadership:** Tasks-oriented leaders clearly defined teachers' goals, job duties, and expectations. This help teachers to be on the same page regarding activities. This led to straightforward Leadership in the school.
4. **Help Teachers to succeed:** Tasks-oriented leaders in school set up clear paths for success for teachers in the school. Tasks-oriented leaders know exactly what they need to do to impress management and advance the teacher's careers. Tasks-oriented leaders focused more on school tasks and how teachers will succeed on each task and responsibility.
5. **Find better systems:** Tasks-oriented leaders in school is key to getting more work done and finding better strategies and systems to carry out the tasks by teachers in the school. Tasks-oriented leaders in school are likely prone to cutting unnecessary tasks and focusing only on the main school task. This help to improve school achievement and performance.

Disadvantages of being a task-oriented leader

The weakness or disadvantages of task-oriented school leaders include;

1. **Reduce Teacher Morale:** Task-oriented leaders also focused on getting schoolwork done without time for some enjoyment at work. If teachers don't get time to socialize or have a little fun throughout the day in the school this may reduce their morale, possibly leading to less productivity.
2. **High Pressure for Teachers:** Task-oriented leaders are always conscious of deadlines, progress, and productivity which can be so stressful for some teachers.

3. Lack of teachers' Bonding: Task-focused leadership can lead to unhealthy competition among teachers in the school.
4. More burnout of Teachers: Task-inclined leaders may be too focused on work to notice the well-being of their teachers. This can lead to feelings of stress, apathy, or even burnout of teachers in the school.
5. Poor Teachers' Development: Task-inclined leaders focused on attaining school objectives and ignoring teachers' development. Task-inclined leaders focus on goal setting which may help teachers meet the school's objectives, but it may not be helping the teachers to grow as individuals.

Carter, (undated) opined that the weakness of task-oriented leadership is that it ignores the welfare and happiness of the staff. Being focused on the task can result in the leader ignoring some critical issues that may come up within the team or among the teachers. Pushing the staff or teachers to complete the job without paying attention to their personal needs can result in a negative environment within the workplace, which can lead the workforce to be less productive. Benjamin (2021) submitted that the application of task-oriented leadership in the organization decreases staff motivation. Although task-oriented leaders excel at getting the job done, they are not renowned for their people skills. The primary focus of a task-oriented leader is the work itself. Providing support, mentoring and praise to employees is viewed as a distraction that takes time away from what the leader sees as critical activities that are directly related to the job at hand. Workers can become demotivated if they feel powerless to control any aspect of their jobs. Because the task-oriented leader likes to control the situation, his staff may become unhappy and have lower job satisfaction. Compounding the problem is the fact that a task-oriented manager is uninterested in workers' feelings or emotions and sees no value in providing his employees with autonomy.

Carter, (undated) asserted that task-oriented leadership tends to stifle ground-breaking, creative, or spontaneous work. Instead, employees typically follow orders, have fixed deadlines for the projects, and have less or no flexibility in completing the tasks. The team that works under this kind of leadership can often lack interest, inspiration, and enthusiasm to go beyond the limits. With few chances to explore new ideas, the staff gets limited in their ability to develop into more complex job roles. Development and training are formal in this environment, which limits staff development opportunities. Task-oriented leaders employ a decisive and direct management style according to Benjamin (2021) which ignores alternative ideas in the organization. They are skilled at telling people exactly what to do and how to do it. While this is a useful attribute when quick decision-making is needed, the disadvantage of this approach is that the task-oriented leader only has time to consider one opinion -- his own. Task-oriented managers are so focused on getting the job done, they fail to solicit input from employees. This can mean the leader misses opportunities for improvement from the people who know the task best -- the employees who perform the work. The perceived disadvantages of task-oriented leadership according to Benjamin (2021) are often dependent on situational factors and group dynamics. Although a manager in a highly automated, production environment may be successful using the task-oriented approach, a workgroup of professionals or academics is likely to favour participation and want their ideas to be taken into consideration -- particularly when group members are experts in their respective fields and the leader is not. Similarly, although task-oriented leadership can be invaluable when providing a quick and effective response to an emergency, it is much less suited to average, everyday situations.

Task-oriented leadership skills in school include;

- 1. Clarify School objectives:** Task-oriented leaders provide direct instruction for teachers in the school. For example, if you are a social master in the school, the leader will provide details of your functions as a social master in specific simple instructions, deadlines, and targets for the social master to achieve the potential tasks in the office.
- 2. Framework tasks precisely.** Task-oriented leaders in the school provide clear details of tasks for all staff in the school by outlining the mission of the school, listing the essential jobs and then accurately explaining the processes of carrying out each responsibility.
- 3. Set deadlines for school Tasks.** Task-oriented leaders provide a time frame for each task within the school system. Setting deadlines is essential for the teachers to have a sense of achievement in the school's programme and assignments. Set reminders letter to the specific teachers handling specific assignments and ask them to work actively on the programme, which has strict deadlines.
- 4. Supervision and Guidance.** Task-oriented leaders in the school provide clear advice and direction to teachers to avoid mistakes and hassles. Task-oriented leaders in the school permit opportunities to ask questions by teachers. Provide information, resources, research, and other points of clarification. By offering guidance, you will address obstacles and move another step towards progress.
- 5. Excellent Appointment:** Task-oriented leaders in schools appoint teachers to different offices. Task-oriented leaders know very well which teacher is suitable for a particular task in the school. Task-oriented leaders are great at proper delegations in the school. They drive productivity levels higher by identifying the strengths of their teachers.

Application of Task-Oriented Leadership Style by School Administrators

School administrators in Nigerian educational institutions can apply a task-oriented leadership style to solve some common schools challenges such as low teachers' job performance and poor students' academic performance in schools across the country.

Application of Task-Oriented Leadership Style to Improve Teacher's Job Performance in School

Most Nigerian educational institutions are faced with the problem of teachers' laziness and low teachers' productivities. The teachers' job performance is critical to the development of the school. Zaifada, Olowonefa, & Ogunode, (2023) submitted that teachers' job performance is the level of attainment of the instructor's tasks and assignments in the school. Teachers' job performance is the act or process by which the teachers execute the official responsibilities in the schools. Teachers' job performance includes writing lesson notes, and lesson plan, organization of laboratory instruments or teaching-learning materials, assigning tests and examinations, marking of scripts, representing the school, extra-curriculum activities and motivating students. The teachers' job performances are all activities and programmes the teachers carry out in the school and the extent to which the activities are achieved.

Teachers' job performance according to Zaifada, et al (2023) is the degree to which teachers execute their official responsibilities in the school. Teachers' job performance is the capacity to effectively inculcate the three domains such as cognitive, psychomotor and affective in the learners. Teachers' job performance covers the roles of the teachers to substitute for the parent's roles in the schools. A teacher's job performance is the duties performed by a teacher in a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals (Obilade as cited in

Selamat & Tautig, 2013). Teachers' job performance could be measured through teachers' job satisfaction and job attitudes such as job commitment, feelings of job challenge, job meaningfulness and job responsibility.

It has been observed that many public school teachers in Nigeria are lazy in terms of discharging their responsibilities in schools in Nigeria (Abdul, 2016). Femi (2014) observed that some teachers instead of teaching rather go and be marketing their products in the schools. Akin (2014) submitted that some teachers are busy gossiping in the school while others are not coming to school regularly. School administrators in such institutions can adopt a task-oriented leadership style to solve the problems of teachers' failure to carry out their official tasks and responsibilities. Task-oriented leaders allocate tasks to workers and ensure the tasks are done without any complaints. Task-oriented leaders supervise workers and provide them with all resources to carry out their assignments in the schools. Wanyoko, & Muchanje, (2021) observed that task-oriented leaders are interested in the productivity of staff with little concern for the welfare of workers. This type of leadership stresses the use of authority to control subordinates. Task-oriented leadership demotivates employees who feel the need for inclusion in the contribution of the organization's policy. On the other hand, task-oriented leadership is effective in institutions where subordinates are lazy and with low productivity. Chan (2014) agreed that task-oriented leadership is essential when there is too much freedom in the institution and low productivity from workers. Wang & Guan (2018) noted that task-oriented leaders have all the control of decisions in an organization and make choices depending on their ideas and preferences and rarely allow subordinates to contribute to decision-making. Task-oriented leaders provide clear expectations of what is to be done and how it should be done. They make decisions independently with or without no input from their subordinates. Task-oriented leaders outline tasks to be done and demand error-free results. Authoritarian principals make all decisions to be followed, supervise them and are only concerned with the job processes.

Wang & Guan (2018) stated that the effects of principals' task-oriented leadership style on teachers depend on certain conditions and may influence the relationship between task-oriented leadership and students' achievement. A study conducted in the Delta State of Nigeria by Duze (2012) on leadership styles of principals and job performance of staffs reported that the job performance of staffs was affected by leadership styles: autocratic, democratic and transformational to greater and lesser extents depending on the prevailing circumstances of the school. Duze (2012) alluded that most principals, however, have not considered the effect of leadership style on teachers' job performance and by extension students' academic achievement. Leadership styles occupy a great position in school management. Principals' task-oriented leadership style influences the relationship with teachers and the decision-making process. Schools have many objectives to achieve but the emphasis is always placed on the student's achievement in academics and co-curricular activities. The expectations of parents are excellent achievement for their children.

Improves Students' Academic Performance in External and Internal Examinations

In recent times the education stakeholders in Nigeria have talked about the falling standard of education lamenting on poor performance of students in both internal and external examinations. The poor performance of students in examinations can be caused by many factors such as the failure of the teachers to carry out the assigned responsibilities of teaching the students in the classrooms what they are supposed to be taught. Femi (2018) opined that teachers' failure to cover the scheme of work and syllabus is a major cause of mass failure in the school system in Nigeria.

Zaifada, et al (2023) observed that students' academic performance is the level of achievement the students attained through academic activities in the school within a set time. A student's academic performance is the extent of positive changes that a learner received within a period in school. Students' academic performance can be defined as learners' capacity to approach and solve academic problems confidently as well as having the power with resilience spirit in the stiff competition for space in academic matters. Student's academic performance is the maximum effort made by students in an examination which is translated into grades or positions as distinction, excellence, credit and merits (Zaifada, et al (2023). Academic performance refers to a student's success in achieving educational goals and reflects how well students achieve the standards set by an academic institution or by the local educational authorities (Steinmayr, Meißner, Weidinger, & Wirthwein, 2014). Ijaiya (2004) asserted that student academic performance refers to the standard that students should be able to know and be able to do.

The problem of poor students' academic performance can be solved by school administrators in Nigeria by employing a task-oriented leadership style. Task-oriented leadership style is a leadership style that focused on a particular organizational task and ensures it is been executed as planned. This leadership style can be used in educational institutions where the student's academic performance is poor. The application of the task-oriented leadership style will help to restructure school task allocation among teachers considering professionalism, experiences, qualification and skills. Teachers will be given a task they can carry out with the adequate provision of resources to execute the task. Teachers are given targets and deadlines to achieve the target under a task-oriented leadership style.

Many studies have established principals' leadership styles on students' academic performance in schools. A study carried out in the USA on teachers' perception of principals' leadership styles on students' achievement by Hardman (2011) found that principals' leadership styles affect students' achievement positively. Another study by Teri, Barbara & Lucindia (2013) of the USA in a study on leadership and students' achievement across societal cultures found that leadership approaches that principals apply are significant in predicting students' achievement. A study in Australian secondary schools (OECD, 2003) found that leadership impact is predominantly related to the student's academic achievement via the more direct influence exerted upon how teachers organize and conduct their instruction. Also, A study conducted by Harerimana & Adegoke (2017) in Kigali Rwanda on the influence of leadership styles on students' achievement found that leadership styles influenced students' achievement in academics. Wangui (2007) and Muli (2005) on leadership styles on students' performance found that the leadership style that a principal uses influences students' achievement whereas task-oriented leaders posted high mean scores in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE). In the task-oriented leadership style in specific, Wanyoko, & Muchanje, (2021) discovered that principals who practised task-oriented leadership style posted high mean marks in KCSE.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Task-oriented leadership style is a leadership style that is task inclined. The leaders here focus more on the task of individual workers and the institution's goals. Task-oriented leadership style is one of the few leadership style school administrators can employ to solve the various challenges their schools are faced with. Specifically, in Nigeria, low teachers' job performance and poor students' academic performance have been identified as major issues in educational institutions. This paper examined the importance of adopting a task-oriented leadership style in addressing specific educational problems in educational institutions in Nigeria. The paper concluded that task-oriented leadership styles can be used in specific school challenges. The

paper also discovered that a task-oriented leadership style can be used to improve teachers' job performance and students' academic performance in educational institutions in Nigeria. Based on this, the paper recommended

1. That school administrators should be more flexible in adopting a leadership style that will enable the teachers to feel a sense of belonging, be motivated, and promote a collaborative working environment towards achieving the school objectives
2. Teaching Service Commission should organize regular in-service programmes for teachers to improve their skills and methods of teaching for better teachers' job performance in the school.
3. School administrators in Nigeria should learn more about the task-oriented leadership style so that they can adopt it whenever it is necessary.
4. The Education agencies should expose school administrators to constant capacity-building programmes that are leadership style inclined.

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